

Crimemalta Observatory

ANNUAL
CRIME
REVIEW
2024

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March 2025

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The Maltese Islands' crime rate has once again declined, with reported crimes falling by 1% in 2024 over the year before. With a population of 563,443 and a total of 16,662 crimes, the trend continued to decline.

With a decline from 45 crimes per 1,000 individuals in 2004 to 30 in 2024, the statistics show that the islands are very safe in terms of crimes per 1,000 persons. Notably, the actual 16,662 reported crimes were much lower than anticipated, despite population increase over the years suggesting a predicted crime rate of 25,820 (based on 2004 statistics) or 21,592 (based on 2014 data).

When compared to the EU average, Malta is placed amongst the safer countries, placed in the lower league for theft and sexual violence, signifying that whilst in most crimes Malta is safer, there is still work to be carried out. This drive is highlighted by the post-crime action, whereas per previous years, homicides in 2024 were solved within a few days, continuing the 100% clearance rate for cases reported from 2018 to 2024.

The homicide rate in 2024 stood at 0.7 per 100,000 persons, lower than the 1.7 recorded in 2004, 2012, and 2022, though slightly up from 0.4 in 2023. Violent crimes also saw a decline to 344 cases in 2024. While theft has increased in certain categories, particularly entertainment-related thefts and pickpocketing, which rose from 405 cases in 2023 to 650 in 2024, this highlights the ongoing need for public awareness and vigilance. Reports of domestic violence continued their yearly increase since 2007, reaching 2,225 cases, with psychological harm accounting for 78% of these.

Additionally, grievous bodily harm due to physical force saw a rise. Despite some category-specific increases, significant declines were recorded in computer misuse, damages, and fraud. Armed robberies and vehicle thefts were the lowest ever recorded. Reports of residential theft remained low at 513 cases, the second lowest ever, following 2023's record low of 479 cases. Arson also remains among the lowest levels recorded in the past 20 years. Geographically, the RISC model identified Mdina as having a crime rate more than five times the national average (due to its small size compared to the number of visitors), while San Ġiljan, Mosta, Floriana, and Valletta fell within the 2x to 5x category.

However, most localities now fall within or below the national rate, with 17 localities in the slightly higher (1x to 2x) category. Gozo saw a notable 23% decrease in crime reports, with the lowest theft figures recorded in the past 20 years. As crime trends evolve, the data underscores the importance of continued vigilance and public awareness to sustain these positive developments

Professor Saviour Formosa

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Crimemalta Annual Crime Review

In 2008, CrimeMalta was launched as a conveyor for crime research and reporting in the Maltese Islands. As from 2017, the annual report is being published through the enhanced CrimeMalta Observatory initiative, which is targeted to expand its reporting to other areas inclusive of environmental, locational and other societal domains.

The annual report covers a factual crime review of Malta’s interactive spatial technologies and spatial statistics such as published in this year’s annual report for 2024.

This report covers the 2024 annual statistics as elicited from an analysis of reported crime, incarceration statistics and spatial analysis. The outputs below pertain to the closed ‘accounts’ for 2024 crime.

This year the statistics cover comparisons between 2023-2024, 2014-24 and 2004-2024 as it is pertinent to enhance the analysis based on a single year gap, a decadal gap and a two-decade gap. This allows for an analysis of crime as Malta experienced a veritable population jump against which to analyse the generational difference in population and crime structure.

The background against which this report is published posits a narrative where the Maltese Islands registered **18,388 crimes in 2004 against a population of 408,798 persons** towards one registering **16,653 crimes in 2014 where the population was that of 434,558 persons** to one where the number of crimes registered **16,662 crimes in 2024 against a population of 563,443 persons**.

Crime Rate per 1000 Persons (2004-2024) with Trend Line

Year	Crimes per 1000 persons
2004	46
2005	46
2006	41
2007	37
2008	34
2009	29
2010	32
2011	34
2012	37
2013	41
2014	38
2015	39
2016	38
2017	37
2018	33
2019	31
2020	25
2021	30
2022	28
2023	31
2024	30

Whilst the **expected** 2024 crime rates based on the 2004 and 2014 data were those of **25,820** and **21,592** respectively, the reported figure of 16,662 crimes still stands in stark contrast to forecasts, experiencing a slight decrease of 193 crimes in 2024. The expected crimes as based on changing population figures show that the observed (reported) crimes are being mitigated as crimes decreased in various categories but experienced significant jumps in offences where awareness by potential victims is required through campaigns. This is due to this year’s analysis which shows that crimes **increased in categories that comprise arson, bodily harm, breach of bail, cruelty to animals, drugs, environmental crime, forgery, pretended rights and theft.** Mobile messaging-based scams and computer-related crime require awareness of potential victimisation before such occurs, experienced a decrease. On the other hand, domestic violence sees no end in sight as figures increase on an annual basis, however the shift towards **psychological harm** has been significant, the latter reaching **78%** of all Domestic Violence cases. Psychological harm increased by 180 cases (12% from 2023), whereas Domestic Violence in its entirety increased by 154 cases or 7%: pointing to decreases in the other sub-categories, except for grievous harm by physical force that increased by 26%.

In summary, at **16,662 reported offences**, a stabilization of the 2023 figures has been registered. This is in contrast to the increase registered in 2023 that had depicted a reversal of previous years’ year-on-year decline through a massive jump in fraudulent gains (which included sms fraud, digital fraud). The latter offences has seen a significant decline in 2024 with a drop of 530 cases (19%). Parallel to this, significant drops in computer-related crimes of 369 cases or a 43% decrease as well as a decrease in damages of 274 cases

(8%) were registered. However, the figures did not decrease to 2022 levels as they were mitigated by increased theft (487 cases or a 10% increase) domestic violence (154 cases or 7%) and a new category of offence entitled environmental crime which registered 174 cases.

It is vital to note that the shift in locational structure that became starkly evident in 2023 where **crime has moved indoors**, is still high at 34% of all crimes. These categories of crimes are potentially out of reach of proactive visual capture through deterrence by community police, mobile units and technologies. Crimes have shifted from the physical outdoor urban construct to an indoor real and virtual construct, where the victim is targeted in their 'safe havens', oftentimes playing a role in the same offence, particularly online fraud. Policing and its effectiveness used to cater for 96% of all crimes within an outdoor setting as at 2004. As virtual and digital realities started shaking the societal norms, in conjunction with new realities such as changes in legislation (domestic violence, money laundering, amongst others), the physical incident component shifted gradually from the outdoors scenario to the indoors one. With 39% of crimes occurring indoors in 2023 and 35% in 2024, within the safety of one's home, out of reach of security services, a need for individual awareness has never been more critical: **from 4% 'indoor' crime in 2004, such jumped to 13% in 2014 and 35% in 2024.**

Inversely, policing experiences with outdoor crime has reached a stage where from 96% in 2004, this shifted to 87% in 2013 and dropping to 65% in 2024. Policing's proactivity is effective but the indoors scenario posits entirely different challenges: it is the individual's foresight of potential victimisation and their eventual action that takes the fore. The need for **awareness of potential victimisation within one's abode has reached**

a state that requires extensive campaigns and awareness-raising activities remains critical.

The year 2024 saw a decrease in crime reports over the 2023-2024 period comprising a **decrease of 193 crimes or 1%**. Comparing same from 2014 and 2004 the 2024 figures show that crime was equivalent to that of **2014** and reduced by **9% from 2004.**

In effect this means that Malta is a safe place as crimes per 1000 persons (the rate employed to analyse total crimes) went down from **45 crimes per 1000 persons** in 2004 to **38 crimes per 1000 persons** in 2014 to **30 crimes per 1000 persons in 2024**, a slight decrease from 2023.

It is to be noted that as police efficiency, technology and societal awareness on safety and security increases, crimes, particularly those that pertained to theft diminish and such pushes the envelope for more serious crimes and new opportunities such as online offences, to become relatively more prominent. The need for awareness in real and virtual worlds is imperative and the need to avoid moral panic instances is even more vital: as crimes of a serious nature occur, the prominence given by society, social and established media could cause the perceived fear of crime to increase. Inversely as trust in the Police Force increases, cases of moral panic will be mitigated through an increased sense of safety and security. This is evidenced as serious crimes are solved in rapid turnarounds, such as the homicides that occurred from **2018 to 2024 were all solved within a few days.** Whilst homicide is a crime that cannot be predicted, the crime rate for this category which averaged **1.0 per 100,000** persons, fell to **0.7 per 100,000** in 2024.

With regards to **violent crimes** that include the Grievous Bodily Harm component across the various crime categories, armed robberies, homicides, violent indecent assault, and violence against public officers registered the same reports as 2024. Whilst in 2012 there were 391 cases registered, such were reduced to **360 cases in 2023**, decreasing in **2024 to 344 cases**.

Last year, the Maltese Islands registered the **lowest number of armed robberies ever**. The **21** reported cases last year represent a third of the reports received in 2005 (61 armed robberies).

Also worth noting is the continued **declining trend of arson reports from 143 reports in 1999 to just 38 cases in 2024**. This is the fourth lowest ever rate of arsons registered in the last 25 years with the three lowest years being the preceding three years under the current headship.

One continuing rapid decrease in crimes over the past decades is due to the fact that the entire crime scenario had been absorbed by a single phenomenon that is the **Theft** category, which phenomenon had registered 62.4% of all crimes in 2004 down to **49.2% in 2014** down to 28.1% in 2023, and inversely as slight increase to **31.3% in 2024** shedding 6,247 crimes since 2004 or 2,981 since 2014. Whilst there were increases in theft (487 cases spread across the recreational and leisure industries as well as pickpocketing), these were offset by the decreases in computer misuse, damages and fraud.

In 2024, the Maltese Islands also registered the **lowest number of theft of vehicles ever**. The **209** such reports received last year represent just 17% of the reports received in 1998.

Similarly, last year the Malta Police received **513 reports of thefts from residence (exterior, occupied or vacant)**. This figure was the second lowest registered by the Malta Police with the lowest ever recorded being the preceding year at 479 (at 34 less than 2024). 2024's number of such

theft reports represent less than half the reports of theft from residences received in 2005 (1102 cases). Theft from **occupied residences**, which averaged 560 crimes over the past two decades, experienced a drop of from 556 offences in 2013 to **359 cases in 2024**.

A review of how society changed over the decades in comparison to 2024, the figures show decreases from 2004, depicted in decreasing rates for theft, attempted offences, damages, violence against public officers, bodily harm, arson, and immigration.

From 2014, depicted in decreasing rates, the decreases were mainly theft, damages, attempted offences, violence against public officers, prostitution, arson and bodily harm.

In contrast, increases in crimes were experienced from 2004 to 2024, depicted in increasing rates, comprised mainly fraud, domestic violence, computer misuse, pretended rights, threats and private violence and environmental crime. **Fraud and computer misuse, the latter two increasing by 1,396% and 4,318%** respectively. From 2014 to 2024, depicted in increasing rates, the increases were registered in fraud, domestic violence, pretended rights computer misuse environmental crime and violence against public officers.

Whilst the **physical-virtual** divide is becoming ever accentuated, one needs to additionally read this report in the new societal dynamic resulting in a context duality defining to the reporting phenomenon: those reflecting actual public-reports and those where the Malta Police were highly effective in their output. The latter includes drugs, forgery, fraud, immigration, money laundering, perjury and false swearing, pornography, prostitution and trafficking of persons.

Highest reported offences

Theft comprised **31.3%** of all offences reported to the Police, increasing from 28.1% in 2022. It is to be noted that there was a generic decrease across the theft sub-categories though significant increases were registered in bars, retail, hotel and restaurants as local and international tourists increased their custom. In addition, **pick-pocketing** reached **650 cases** (3.9% of all crimes). Pick-pocketing has been increasing steadily from 244 cases in 2021, having dropped from 2,447 cases in 2016.

2024 registered the **lowest number of theft of vehicles ever**. The 209 such reports received last year represent just 17% of the reports received in 1998.

The second highest reported offence, **Damages**, has experienced a year-on-year decrease of **8%** decrease between 2023 and 2024 to **18.4%** of all offences in 2024, as compared to 24.7% in 2014 and 19.8% in 2023. Despite the long-term increase over the decades in rate terms, the figure is the lowest since 2013.

At the third ranking, **Fraud** experienced 2,394 cases, specifically pushed by fraudulent gains through mobile, messaging and online payment scams impersonating service, delivery and ancillary services. Down from the record 2,905 cases registered in 2023, the figure is also lower than the **2376** cases registered in 2021. The Fraud category registered 14.4% of all crimes reported in 2024, up from **160** cases in 2004 and 430 in 2014.

In fourth place, **Domestic Violence** at 13.4% comprised the highest percentage registered in this crime category with **2,225 cases in 2024** up from **2,071 cases in 2023**. This decadal massive **112% (1,177 cases) increase** over the

2014-2024 period reflects the vulnerability of victims' situations even though it is morphing in sub-category structure. It is to be noted that from the 2022-2023 increase, **Psychological Harm** increased by 180 cases (12% from 2022), whereas Domestic Violence in its entirety increased by 154 cases or 7%: pointing to decreases in the other sub-categories. Psychological Harm in 2024 accounted for **78% of all domestic violence crimes**. Increases occurred in psychological harm and grievous bodily harm with physical force, whilst the other sub-categories experienced decline or no change in numbers.

Bodily Harm, which had registered a year-on-year increase initiated in 2021, increased in **2024 to 5.9% of all offences**. The the number of reported offences increased by 32 crimes, amounting to 978 cases in 2024.

These 5 categories of crimes comprise 83% of all crime reports.

The Societal Construct

As described in previous reports, the foundations that comprise social structures known as **PREFE** (Politics, Religion, Economy, Family and Education) have experienced rapid change such that the impact of values and norms becomes less tangible. Whilst the Political or legal measures have evolved and security implementation has increased in the social arenas resulting in the reduction of such offences as theft from residences, damages, bodily harm and prostitution, the strongest pillar pertaining to the family or household has become increasingly fragile such that the incidence of the personal-security incidents has grown dramatically. This is reflected through domestic violence, irrespective of form or method, whether psychological or physical. The inclusion of Technology as a new foundational element is essential as it posits scenarios where crime has migrated to the digital domains, both in commissioning and investigation: **PREFET**.

Domestic Violence, as well as threats and private violence increased not only in ratio terms but in actual cases, indicating a drastic increase in personal violence.

As Economic measures increasingly offer most offenders an opportunity to partake to crime when the rewards far exceed the sanctions, offences such as theft emanating from the invasion of person-spaces increase as they offer a quick intake of funds. The fact that the recreation and leisure activities offer ripe ground for offending particularly where the recreational zones are crowded and person space is not possible, the opportunity for dexterous hands offers a high rate of return. This time round, the loss of economic activity, unheard of in recent decades, has in turn rendered the main crime attractor null: as tourism receded, crime took an ominous turn and personal crime took precedence.

The Social Areas, previously dominated by crime committed in the public zone, have in turn become safer. As reported in previous annual reports, the entity responsible for safety and security: the **Malta Police Force**, emerged resurgent and came through for society, both in its strategic preparedness and the Strategy to increase Public Trust as awarded through national and international surveys such as the European Trust Barometer.

Again, the change was impacted by implementation of a **Transformation Strategy**, a continuous shakeup in senior management and the effort to bring on board all officers, whilst affecting a move towards ownership by all officers within a citizen-officer dynamic.

The changes in crime construct, the reduction in serious and long-standing high-ranking offences are resultant also of a three-pronged approach: increased police proactivity, enhanced enforcement and better recording of reports.

Policing and Community intervention was efficiently rendered safer by the Malta Police through its **Community Policing** initiative, expanding the localities' intervention and a **Crime Prevention Strategy**. The setting up of specialised services such as the MPF establishment of a **Gender-Based & Domestic Violence Unit** in 2020. The **Victim Support Agency** is rendering a service on the realities of spiraling domestic violence.

Location

In terms of the loss of relative offence volume that **San Giljan** had experienced over the past years till 2022, going up from 12.5% in 2004 to **16.5% in 2014** eventually decreasing to **5.6% in 2020 (during COVID times), has been inverted** since 2020. This locality has recorded an increase year-on-year reaching **10.5% in 2024**. As recreation and entertainment returned post-covid closure, resulting in an increase in activity in San Giljan, the number of crimes reached **1,753 in 2024**. San Giljan is followed by San Pawl il-Bahar at 8.5% (down from 9.6% in 2023), in turn followed by Birkirkara (4%) and Sliema (3.8%), The town requires mitigation as both the residential component and the touristic/recreational component have increased such that the potential for opportunities for crime increases.

The Gozo Phenomenon

Last year's 174 theft reports in Gozo represent the **lowest ever number** of such cases in Gozo in the past 20 years and almost **half the reported Gozo theft cases in 2006** (332). Comprehensively, 2024 crime reports in Gozo have **declined by a notable 23%** (886) compared to 2023 (1144).

Crimemalta Observatory Background Text:
Morphing Of The Maltese Crime Scenario

**Offences in the Maltese Islands have morphed from
a multi-thematic to a spatial structure**

Crime perception and its presence has taken precedence and will be analysed through a Crime Victimization Survey that will be carried out in 2025.

This will enable the CrimeMalta Observatory to understand what the Dark Figure of Crime and unreported crime figures constitute, why victims opt not to report and which crime categories go unreported. The 100 question survey is targeted for end 2025.

The CrimeMalta Observatory notes that the most serious crimes have experienced mitigation and effort to reduce same even as an observation is made where homicides were **mitigated by the effective closure of all cases since 2018 in a very short time from the date of actuation**. Other offences require more studies and awareness raising as most online crimes are fast-evolving and require new methods to solve. One of the efforts seen concerns the large number of employed experts in the financial crime, cyber crime and domestic crime units, which compete with the private sector for their expert retention.

The past year has again seen an increased awareness process on Domestic Violence as well as the uptake of initiatives projects that study the phenomenon. The Crime Prevention Strategy (Formosa Pace, 2017) and the Victim Support Agency sought for a focus on raising awareness towards the mitigation of crime that integrates further community policing aimed at decreasing the social-space offences further, have been taken up by the relevant entities. The need to focus on the movement away from the perception that mitigation is simply a role that the Police Force must be solely responsible for is erroneous, but one needs to view such as rather a call for collective Social Responsibility.

Previous CrimeMalta Observatory reports pointed towards a depiction where Social Capital is provided through the PREFET structures, of which the Police Force form a part. However, the essential aspects that will pivot towards offence mitigation lie in the enhancement of Social Cohesion through awareness raising, values redefinition, self-respect and the will to report and stop offences. Such a process requires a sea change in both the Police Force and relative enforcement agencies remit as well as civil society through NGOs and self-help groups. The instances where such institutions were attacked on a constant basis have eroded the perception and perceived trust, which the entities need to work on in order to achieve both reduction in offences as well as an increase of knowledge on the actual crime situation based on facts as against social-media depictions or rash statements that go counter to the crime statistics.

One cannot continue to observe crime as the arena for uniformed officers but one where such are enhanced through social and publicity activity run by social entities to ensure knowledge on crime, rescue and support functions as well as personal safety and security increase. It is imperative that offences are viewed as a personal domain issue as against that pertaining to the police. The latter are tasked with securing social spaces, but the individual is tasked with securing their private spaces. This is to be enhanced through the implementation of measures emanating from the **Crime Prevention Strategy**.

On a regional/locality level, crime reports need to be taken seriously as they posit a comparative approach to research methodology that would allow one to make information-based policy and in effect take realistic measures to mitigate crime fluctuations.

Criminologist Professor Saviour Formosa and Dr Formosa Pace (www.crimemaltaobservatory.org) have been publishing crime statistics and reviews since 2008 through the analysis of crime trends in Malta as of 1949 and through spatio-temporal analysis as from 1998 (**431,809 offences**). Crime studies in Malta comprise 44 main categories of crime and 273 subcategories.

The studies take the form of a rate analysis, as against a count analysis, through the study of a RISC assessment (**Relative Index of Spatial Crime**), trend analysis and spatio-statistical analysis.

The RISC categories that show which towns suffer most from crime, or inversely are safest in Malta and Gozo, can be found below.

Over the years a spatial depiction was developed to aid users to visualise crime through maps, where due to the increasingly available mobile technologies, users can interact with their location and identify safety zones as well as offence areas. The 2024 report comprises the publication of interactive maps highlighting graduated maps, heat maps as well as variable high-level cluster maps that users can review and understand safety and security in the Maltese Islands. The categories comprise Main Category Offences, Sub-Category Offences and Heatmaps.

Refer to the CrimeMalta Observatory website for interactive data: www.crimemaltaobservatory.org.

Figures To Ponder: 2023-2024

with notes on the main 2004-2024 offences
(bi-decadal comparison)

Crime perception and its presence has taken precedence and will be analysed through a Crime Victimization Survey that will be carried out in 2025. This will enable the CrimeMalta Observatory to understand what the Dark Figure of Crime and unreported crime figures constitute, why victims opt not to report and which crime categories go unreported.

The 100 question survey is targeted for end 2025.

- **Crimes that Increased:** abuse of public authority, arson, attempted offences, bodily harm, breach of bail conditions, cruelty to animals, domestic violence, drugs, environmental crime, forgery, gender-based violence, homicide, immigration, perjury and false swearing, pornography, pretended rights, theft, threats and private violence, unauthorised access in restricted area.
 - 2004-2024: abandonment of child, abortion, abuse of public authority, breach of bail conditions, computer misuse, crimes against public peace, cruelty to animals, domestic violence, drugs, environmental crime, forgery, fraud, gender based violence, money laundering, perjury and false swearing, pornography, pretended rights, sexual offence, threats and private violence, trafficking of persons, unauthorised access in restricted area, violence against public officer

- **Crimes that Decreased:** abandonment of child, bigamy, computer misuse, crimes against public peace, crimes vs admin of justice etc, damage, erroneous reports, fraud, infanticide, money laundering, prostitution, sexual offence, violation of places of confinement, violence against public officer.
 - 2004-2024: abuses relating to prisons, against morals/honour - family, arson, attempted offences, bigamy, bodily harm, crimes against public peace, crimes against public safety, crimes vs administration of justice etc, damage, homicide, immigration, infanticide/ abandonment of child, prostitution, theft, violation of places of confinement, violence against public officer

- **Arson** represented a particular crime that spreads the fear of crime to high levels. Hovering around 100 cases annually as recorded over the decades, 2024 registered 38 cases, an increase of 4 cases in 2024, one of **the lowest** reported figures since the introduction of PIRS in 1998. Also worth noting is the continued decline trend of arson reports from 143 reports in 1999 to just 38 cases in 2024. This is the fourth lowest ever rate of arsons registered in the last 25 years with the three lowest years being the preceding three years under the current headship.
 - 2004-2024: Decrease of 68% from 120 cases in 2004 to 38 in 2024

- **Thefts**, which have seen an increase of **487 (10%) crimes in 2024** to total **5,218 cases**. As pickpocketing increased from 450 cases to 650, the figures are still lower than the 2,447 figure in 2016 and once more a campaign would help raise awareness. 32 categories of theft experienced no change or a decline whilst 16 categories increased, mainly thefts from bars and restaurants, retail outlets, theft from seacraft and theft from vehicle exterior and interior.
 - 2004-2024: Decrease of 54% from 6,247 cases in 2004 to 5,218 in 2024

- **Damages**, at **3,062 cases** in 2024, decreased by 8% decrease between 2023 and 2024 to 18.4% of all offences in 2024, down from 19.8% in 2023. The decrease was due to cases of involuntary damage by hit and run and involuntary damage by other categories.
 - 2004-2024: Decrease of 16% from 3,657 cases in 2004 to 3,336 in 2024

- **Bodily Harm**, at **978 cases** in 2024, **increased by 3%**. The main increase was related to Grievous and Slight Bodily Harm by physical force.
 - 2004-2024: Decrease of 8% from 1,065 cases in 2004 to 978 in 2024

- **Fraud** has experienced a **decrease of 511 cases (18%)**. The cases reached 2,394 cases in 2024 (14.4% of all crimes), down from 2,905 cases in 2023.
 - 2004-2024: Increase of 1,396% from 160 cases in 2004 to 2,394 in 2024

- **Computer** related crime experienced a **43% decrease in 2024**, totaling 486 cases down from 855 cases in 2024, mainly through Unauthorised Access.
 - 2004-2024: Increase of 4,318% from 11 cases in 2004 to 486 in 2024

- **Drugs increased by 16 cases (8%)** in 2024, following an increase of 435 cases between 2020 and 2021 and a decrease in 2022 and 2023). The change over the recent years is principally the result of increased road checks and more targeted policing coupled with better capturing of reports by the Drugs Squad which traditionally might have not been entering the serious cases in the PIRS.
 - 2004-2024: Increase of 177% from 78 cases in 2004 to 216 in 2024

- **Domestic Violence increased by 7%, (154 cases) from 2,071 cases in 2023 to 2,225 cases in 2024** (6.5% of all 2024 cases). Psychological Harm increased by 180 cases (12% from 2023) and comprises 78% of all domestic violence cases. Note that the first full reporting year was in 2008 following the change in legislation in 2007.
 - 2008-2022: Increase of 394% from 450 cases in 2008 to 2,225 in 2024

- **Immigration** experienced an **increase of 11%** in reporting (reporting 69 cases up from 62 in 2023). This is another offence that experienced a dual operational change: enhanced enforcement of immigration laws as well as steering away from the traditional practice that the Immigration Section did not record its operations in the PIRS. Thus, the increase reflects the result of better reports capturing exposing the full picture of actions taken by the police.
 - 2004-2024: Decrease of 44% from 123 cases in 2004 to 69 in 2024

- **Threats and Private Violence decreased by 4% in 2024** to 401 cases, decreasing mainly through harassment and threats by means of writing.
 - 2004-2024: Increase of 286% from 104 cases in 2004 to 401 in 2024

- **Sexual Offences decreased by 9% in 2024** to 163 cases decreasing in defilement of minors and violent indecent assault but increasing in the other sub-categories.
 - 2004-2024: Increase of 167% from 61 cases in 2004 to 163 in 2024

- **Violence against Public Officers decreased by 1% to 143 cases** down from 144 in 2023, a steady year-on-year decrease since 2017. Whilst several factors could be at play, the introduction of body-worn cameras in the first half of 2021 is playing a critical role. Note the changes wrought to the law that further protects such officials, which should result in further decreases in reporting.
 - 2004-2024: Increase of 29% from 111 cases in 2004 to 143 in 2024

- **Theft from Occupied Residences reached 359 cases up from 297 cases in 2023.** Theft from the exterior decreased by 2% whilst theft from vacant residences decreased by 31%. In 2024, the Maltese Islands received **513 reports of thefts from residence (exterior, occupied or vacant).** This figure was the second lowest registered by the Malta Police with the lowest ever recorded being the preceding year at 479 (34 less). Last year's number of such theft reports represent less than half the reports of theft from residences received in 2005 (1,102 cases).
 - 2008-2023: Decrease of 36% from 565 cases in 2008 to 359 in 2024

- **Pretended Rights** which had been recorded as a separate category in 2017 registered a **20% increase** in reports amounting to 415 cases in 2024 up from 346 cases in 2023. This offence has registered steady increases year on year.
 - 2017-2024: Increase of 192% from 142 cases in 2017 to 415 in 2024

- **Money Laundering** as recorded for the first time as a distinct category in 2017, registered 60 cases resulting in a **28% decrease** in 2024, down from 180 cases in 2021 and 83 cases in 2023. It is to be noted that the overall increase since the introduction in 2017 relates to the better capturing of reports by the Malta Police in the reporting system.
 - 2017-2023: Increase of 253% from 17 cases in 2017 to 60 in 2024

- **Gender-Based Violence** which was introduced in 2020, when 2 cases were registered, whilst **5 cases were registered in 2024.** 2 cases were registered during 2023.
 - 2020-2023: Increase of 150% from 2 cases in 2020 to 5 in 2024

- **Cruelty to Animals** was introduced as a new category in 2024, when 20 cases were registered.

- **Environmental Crimes** was introduced as a new category in 2024, when 174 cases were registered.

Change in Reported Offences from 2004 to 2024

Stacked Bar Chart of Selected Offences from 2005 to 2024

Annual change in Reported Main Offences by Year 2004 - 2024

Temporal Statistics

In terms of Monthly statistics, January, February, April, August and September registered increases.

Monday remained the main attractor for most incidences though Thursdays, Fridays and Saturdays registered increases.

In terms of time of crime, increases occurred during most hours with the main increases occurring between **22:00 and 06:00**, which is interesting as previously the latest hour for reporting was 03:00, indicating an extension of the activities till late into the night. As the recreational areas regain its attraction value, main offences occur during these times as reflected by the increase in crime categories related to the entertainment, recreation and touristic domains.

Another spike at 08:00 and 19:00 indicates that offences occurred at this specific time which also points to residence-related offences, when residents arrive home, which requires further study to ensure mitigation.

Prisons In Malta

Prison numbers registered the highest ever figures in recorded history, reaching 908 residents on the 27th of November 2020. On the last Friday 27 December 2024, 691 residents were registered.

CSA (formerly CCF) remains inundated with a high number of inmates, held in the Island's only prison that comprises services for both sexes, all categories of offences, all ages, national and international provenance, sentenced and remanded offenders, amongst other categories. Youths have been transferred to Mtahleb.

As from 2012, CrimeMalta Observatory's research process was also enhanced to include the prison population statistics, with data going back to 2001.

Some statistics recorded on a Friday base-date:

- The CSA Population as of **27th December 2024** (last Friday): 691 (632 males and 59 females);
- The CCF Population as at the **highest 2024 recorded Friday** – 23rd February 2024 registering 695 inmates (647 males and 48 females).
- The CrimeMalta Observatory website depicts an interactive graduated map showing the countries that most residents hail from the **1950s and after**.
- The CCF/CSA experienced residents from **100 foreign countries**.

Risc Model: League Tables For 2024

As part of a review of RISC Modelling for the Maltese Islands, a number of analytical studies have been carried out for the period between 1998 and 2024. Domestic Violence and Commercial Activity-related RISC has been included as of 2015.

Note: The national rate of offences, which is calculated as the observed offences as against those which should potentially occur in those areas under study.

Grand Total Offences

In terms of Grand Total Offences, the highest category, that ranking at 5 times or higher than the national rate, Mdina took pole position.

At a rate between 2 and 5 times the national rate, San Giljan, Mosta, Floriana and Valletta were registered. At a rate between the national up to twice that rate one can find Marsa, Gudja (includes Airport), Paola, Bormla, San Pawl Il-Bahar, Msida, Ta' Xbiex, Luqa, Hamrun, Zebbug (Ghawdex), Mellieha, Birgu, Ghajnsielem, Birzebbugia, Gzira, Santa Lucija, Marsaxlokk.

All the other Councils host a lower than national rate, albeit none have a Zero RISC.

Council	Council	Council	Council
MDINA	SAN GILJAN	MARSA	SLIEMA
	MOSTA	GUDJA	RABAT (Victoria)
	FLORIANA	PAOLA	ZEJTUN
	VALLETTA	BORMLA	QORMI
		SAN PAWL IL-BAHAR	KIRKOP
		MSIDA	KALKARA
		TA' XBIEX	PIETA
		LUQA	IKLIN
		HAMRUN	RABAT (Malta)
		ZEBBUG (Ghawdex)	FGURA
		MELLIEHA	MARSASCALA
		BIRGU	BIRKIRKRARA
		GHAJNSIELEM	
		BIRZEBBUGIA	
		GZIRA	
		SANTA LUCIJA	
		MARSAXLOKK	

Theft from Residences

Whilst this category of offences registered Munxar as having over 5 times the national rate of offences in 2024. The relative RISC registered Xghajra, Zebbug (Ghawdex), Mosta, Msida and Valletta within the 2x-5x RISC. The rate between the national up to twice that rate category includes Attard, Iklin, Gzira, Swieqi, Pieta, Birzebbugia, Bormla, Santa Lucija, Balzan, Paola, Fgura, Ghajnsielem, San Giljan, San Lawrenz, Zabbar, Marsascala, San Gwann, Isla, Rabat (Malta), Luqa, Xewkija, Kercem and Munxar. In contrast, most other zones have lower than average rates and Mdina and Fontana registered zero residential offences in 2024.

Council	Council	Council	Council
XGHAJRA	ATTARD	NADUR	MDINA
ZEBBUG (Ghawdex)	IKLIN	KALKARA	FONTANA
MOSTA	GZIRA	GUDJA	
MSIDA	SWIEQI	MARSA	
VALLETTA	PIETA	PEMBROKE	
	BIRZEBBUGIA	ZEJTUN	
	BORMLA		
	SANTA LUCIJA		
	BALZAN		
	PAOLA		
	FGURA		
	GHAJNSIELEM		
	SAN GILJAN		
	SAN LAWRENZ		
	ZABBAR		
	MARSASCALA		
	SAN GWANN		
	ISLA		
	RABAT (Malta)		
	LUQA		
	XEWKIJA		
	KERCEM		
	MUNXAR		

Theft of and from Vehicles

During 2024, Floriana ranked at 5 times or higher than the national rate, followed by Marsa, Birzebbugia, Paola, Qormi, Bormla as the highest RISC areas where one's car could be vandalised, broken into and/or stolen, which towns host between 2 and 5 times the national rate. Note that these towns host parking and transport-related activities that attract offenders to high-volume and relatively less monitored opportunities. Kercem, San Lawrenz, Xaghra, Sannat, Gharb, Qala, Ghasri and Fontana hosted zero offences.

Council	Council	Council	Council
FLORIANA	IKLIN	SAN PAWL IL BAHAR	KERCEM
MARSA	KIRKOP	BALZAN	SAN LAWRENZ
BIRZEBBUGA	LUQA	SAN GWANN	XAGHRA
PAOLA	SANTA LUCIJA	GHAJNSIELEM	SANNAT
QORMI	SAN GILJAN	BIRKIRKARA	GHARB
BORMLA	MOSTA	ZEBBUG (Malta)	QALA
	MSIDA	MELLIEHA	GHASRI
	PIETA	ISLA	FONTANA
	GUDJA	LIJA	
	TA' XBIEX	ZURRIEQ	
	HAMRUN	XGHAJRA	
	VALLETTA	SAFI	
	TARXIEN	FGURA	
	BIRGU	SLIEMA	
	GHARGHUR	ATTARD	
	SIGGIEWI	MUNXAR	
	ZABBAR	MQABBA	
	ZEBBUG (Ghawdex)	RABAT (Malta)	
	KALKARA	RABAT (Victoria)	
	MDINA	NADUR	
	MARSAXLOKK	XEWKIJA	
		SWIEQI	
		MTARFA	
		QRENDI	
		DINGLI	
		MGARR	

Domestic Violence

Domestic violence reports pertain to stalking, slight bodily harm, grievous bodily harm and psychological harm. Mosta, Floriana, Bormla, Safi and Santa Lucija host between 2 and 5 the national rate. With diminishing rates of RISC, it is imperative to note that a significant number of councils exhibit some form of domestic violence that is above the national rate (yellow in the RISC maps depicted in the CrimeMalta Observatory website) at 1-2 times the rate. In effect all towns have incident reporting but may register lower than national rates.

At the other end of the scale, Fontana and Ghasri registered zero offences, a phenomenon also found in rural and small areas where the changes in legislation may yet have an effect in terms of encouraging victims to report.

Council	Council	Council	Council
MOSTA	BIRZEBBUGIA	ZEBBBUG (Malta)	ZEBBBUG (Ghawdex)
FLORIANA	VALLETTA	XGHAJRA	SLIEMA
BORMLA	ZEJTUN	TARXIEN	QALA
SAFI	HAMRUN	GHARGHUR	TA' XBIEX
SANTA LUCIJA	BIRGU	SAN GWANN	BALZAN
	FGURA	RABAT (Victoria)	MTARFA
	GUDJA	NAXXAR	NADUR
	LUQA	SIGGIEWI	SWIEQI
	ZABBAR	SAN PAWL IL BAHAR	GHARB
	MARSA	XAGHRA	SAN LAWRENZ
	KIRKOP	QRENDI	XEWKIJA
	PAOLA	MARSAXLOKK	KERCEM
	QORMI	ISLA	SANNAT
	LIJA	KALKARA	MGARR
	MARSASCALA	RABAT (Malta)	FONTANA
	MQABBA	IKLIN	GHASRI
	MDINA	ATTARD	
	PIETA	SAN GILJAN	
	GHAXAQ	MSIDA	
	SANTA VENERA	MUNXAR	
	BIRKIRKARA	DINGLI	
	ZURRIEQ	PEMBROKE	
		GZIRA	
		MELLIEHA	
		GHAJNSIELEM	

Commercial Activity-related

There were no localities hosting more than 5 times the national rate. Towns that host between 2 and 5 times the national rate of offences comprise San Giljan, Gudja (including Airport) and Ghaxaq. The least RISC registering towns at zero RISC include San Lawrenz, Kirkop, Dingli, Munxar, Mdina, Qrendi, Nadur, Fontana, Xghajra, Isla, Kercem, Qala, Ghasri and Gharb.

Council	Council	Council	Council
SAN GILJAN	SLIEMA	LUQA	MQABBA
GUDJA	PEMBROKE	TA' XBIEX	IKLIN
GHAXAQ	MELLIEHA	GHAJNSIELEM	ZEBBUG (Ghawdex)
	BIRKIRKARA	ATTARD	ZEBBUG (Malta)
	SAFI	ZABBAR	XAGHRA
	BORMLA	LIJA	BALZAN
	SAN PAWL IL BAHAR	MTARFA	SAN LAWRENZ
	XEWKIJA	MARSA	KIRKOP
	GZIRA	MARSASCALA	DINGLI
	FGURA	MARSAXLOKK	MUNXAR
	SIGGIEWI	NAXXAR	MDINA
	HAMRUN	KALKARA	QRENDI
	SWIEQI	MOSTA	NADUR
	VALLETTA	PAOLA	FONTANA
	MSIDA	SANTA LUCIJA	XGHAJRA
	ZEJTUN	PIETA	ISLA
		QORMI	KERCEM
		ZURRIEQ	QALA
		SANNAT	GHASRI
		SANTA VENERA	GARB
		RABAT (Victoria)	
		BIRGU	
		BIRZEBBUGIA	
		RABAT (Malta)	
		TARXIEN	
		FLORIANA	
		MGARR	
		GHARGHUR	
		SAN GWANN	

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Reference Maps

Main site: www.crimemaltaobservatory.org

- Main Crime Categories Interactive Map
- Main Crime Sub Categories Interactive Map
- Heat Maps
- Pickpocketing Maps

Interactive Cluster Map

Interactive Heat Map

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